

Syntheses of 1,5-Benzothiazepines. Part-VIII. Syntheses of 2,4-(Substituted-diaryl)-8-ethoxy-2,5-dihydro-1,5-benzothiazepines

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The presence of a substituent in the fused benzene ring of 1,4-benzodiazepine and 1,5-benzodiazepines and no substituent in the fused benzene ring in 1,5-benzothiazepine drugs inspired us to carry out the syntheses of a series of new 1,5-benzothiazepines (3a-f) having an ethoxyl group in fused benzene ring and differently substituted aryl groups at positions 2 and 4. Since chalcones, when reacted with substituted aminobenzenethiols in neutral medium, gave satisfactory yields of the products¹, we carried out the reactions of 2-amino-5-ethoxybenzenethiol (1) with different chalcones having various substituents in ring A and B (2a-f) in toluene to obtain the desired 2,4-(substituted-diaryl)-8-ethoxy-2,5-dihydro-1,5-benzothiazepines (3a-f) (Scheme 1). The characterisation of 3a-f was carried out by elemental analyses, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral studies.

Results and Discussion

The absence of characteristic carbonyl and amino peaks in the ir spectra pointed to the satisfactory single step syntheses of title compounds. Broad absorption bands at 3 155–3 145 cm⁻¹ showed the presence of N–H. Aromatic pattern was shown by the absorptions at 3 050–3 000, 1 600–1 590, 1 575–1 570 and 760–750 cm⁻¹. Besides, the ν_{asym} aryl-O–C absorptions were obtained at 1 250–1 240 and δ aryl-O–C at 1 385–1 375 cm⁻¹. Assignments were also made for $\nu_{\text{C-Cl}}$ at 780 (3a), 795 (3b) and 820 cm⁻¹ (3c), while 3e and 3f showed ν_{OH} band at 3 240 and 3 300 cm⁻¹ respectively.

In ¹H nmr spectra, 3a, 3b and 3f gave 3H singlets at δ 3.64, 3.68 and 3.62 respectively due to the OCH₃ group. Singlets corresponding to six protons (δ 2.80–2.84) in 3c and 3d were due to N(CH₃)₂ group. All spectra showed the signals at δ 3.66–3.80 (1H, b, NH), 1.12–1.28 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH₃) and 3.40–3.60 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, C₈–OCH₂CH₃). The

- 3a. R=2-Cl, R'=4-OCH₃
 b. R=4-Cl, R'=4-OCH₃
 c. R=4-N(CH₃)₂, R'=4-Cl
 d. R=4-N(CH₃)₂, R'=H
 e. R=4-OH, R'=H
 f. R=1-OCH₃, R'=2-OH

Scheme 1

absorptions in the range δ 6.04–7.36 appear as multiplets due to the absorption of 13/14 protons, 11/12 aromatic and two protons on vicinal carbons, C-2 and C-3. This is contrary to the ABX pattern observed in the case of the imino form. The presence of NH is also supported by the ir band at 3 155–3 145 cm⁻¹. All these observations support

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	5-H (b)	8-H (OCH ₂ CH ₂) (J 7 Hz)	OCH ₃	CH ₃	ArH C ₂ -H, C ₃ -H
3b	87	55	3.74	1.24 (3H, t) 3.52 (2H, q)	3.68 (3H, s)	—	6.08–7.16 (13H, m)
c	90	65	3.68	1.20 (3H, t) 3.48 (2H, q)	—	2.80 (6H, s)	6.04–7.24 (13H, m)
d	85	55	3.66	1.16 (3H, t) 3.48 (2H, q)	—	2.84 (6H, s)	6.04–7.28 (14H, m)
e	100	62	3.80	1.28 (3H, t) 3.60 (2H, q)	—	—	6.16–7.36 (14H, m)
f	78	58	3.80	1.20 (3H, t) 3.44 (2H, q)	3.62 (3H, s)	—	6.12–7.04 (13H, m)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

the enamine form, i.e. the 2,5-dihydro structure instead of 2,3-dihydro structure² (imino form).

The mass spectra showed m/z M^+ and $[M+2]^+$ peaks at 423, 436, 402 and 375; 425, 438, 404 and 377 corresponding to 3a, 3c, 3d and 3e respectively. In accordance with the nitrogen rule, the molecular ion peaks of 3a and 3e appeared at odd numbers while 3c and 3d at even numbers. The isotopic peaks $[M+2]^+$ of appreciable intensity [34% of M^+] of 3a and 3e showed the presence of chlorine. 3a and 3e also gave $[M+4]^+$ peaks at 427 and 440 respectively. The $[M+2]^+$ and $[M+4]^+$ peaks were observed due to the presence of Cl and S.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infracord 577 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) either on a Perkin-Elmer R-12-B-60 MHz or a Jeol FT 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Varian Match-7 instrument at 70 eV.

Tlc was used to test the purity of the compounds (3a–f) using the solvent system, benzene-ethanol-ammonia (7 : 2 : 1) on silica gel G.

The chalcones (2a–f) were prepared by the condensation of appropriately substituted benzaldehydes with substituted acetophenones in the presence of ethanol and alkali. While 2b was obtained at room temperature, 2a required external cooling. 2c was obtained after heating the reaction mixture on a water-bath and 2d–f required dilution and neutralisation with acetic acid. Before dilution and neutralisation were done, variation in the

temperatures of reaction mixtures was made as : 2d left at room temperature for 20 h, 2e heated upto 70° for 2 h and left at room temperature for 3 days and 2f warmed at 60° for 2 h.

2-Amino-5-ethoxy-benzenethiol (1) was prepared by literature method⁸.

4-(p-Anisyl)-2-(2-chlorophenyl)-8-ethoxy-2,5-dihydro-1,5-benzothiazepine (3a): To a solution of 2-amino-5-ethoxy-benzenethiol (1; 0.001 mol) in dry toluene (10 ml), 2-chlorobenzal-4'-methoxyacetophenone (2a; 0.001 mol) was added with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h when it turned dark brown. Removal of toluene under reduced pressure gave a brown solid which on washing with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and crystallisation from dry ethanol gave yellow crystals (0.20 g, 48%), m.p. 124° (Found: C, 67.85; H, 5.13; N, 3.25. C₂₄H₂₂NO₂SCl requires: C, 68.00; H, 5.19; N, 3.30%); R_f 0.86; ν_{max} 3 145 (NH), 1 245 (ν_{asym} aryl-O-C) and 780 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ 3.68 (1H, b, NH), 6.16 (1H, d, J 6 Hz, C₂-H), 7.32 (1H, d, J 6 Hz, C₃-H), 3.64 (3H, s, OCH₃), [1.12 (3H, t, J 7 Hz) and 3.40 (2H, q, J 7 Hz) OCH₂CH₂] and 6.28–7.28 (11H, m, ArH); M^+ 423, $[M+2]^+$ 425 and $[M+4]^+$ 427.

3b–f (Table 1) were similarly prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-amino-5-ethoxybenzenethiol (1) with the respective chalcones (2b–f).

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